

**EFFICACY OF MUDGAPUSHPADI KWATH YONIDHAVAN IN KAPHAJ YONIVYAPAD:
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ABSTRACT

A healthy woman is a promise of a healthy family. The concept of healthy yoni has been asserted in various phases of a woman's life, from puberty to menopause, the concept of healthy yoni has been mentioned in Ayurveda as well as in modern. Due to change in lifestyle, modern food habits of fast food, junk food she is unable to follow the rules of *Dincharya*, *Rutucharya*, *Rajaswala*, *Rutumati* and *Sutikaparicharya* which are explained by Acharyas for women's health. Thus she is prone to various *yonirogas*, one of which is *Yonigat Shewta-Picchilsrava*, *Yonikandu*, *Yonigata Alpavedana* which are the features of Kaphajyonivyapada and is neglected by women as minor symptoms. Now a days, infection related to yoni is a burning problem irrespective of their age or socioeconomic status. Due to infection. there may be sign and symptoms like vaginal discharge, itching, coldness. In Ayurveda, these types of sign and symptoms are found in *Kaphaja yoni vyapad* and some of symptoms are similar with Non Specific Vulvovaginitis. Gynaecological disorders have found its immense importance in the field of medicine due to fact that women have a unique function of giving birth. In Ayurveda, women health care is related in separate section, where the term *Yoni vyapad* includes majority gynaecological disorders. Before knowing the management, literature of the disease should be known. Therefore, in this study an effort has been put forth to make a literary study covering almost all the aspects of Kaphajyonivyapad as per Ayurveda and modern.

KEY WORDS: Ayurveda kaphaj Yonivyapad, Vaginal discharge.**INTRODUCTION**

A specific group of the diseases of women i.e. *yonivyapad* has been mentioned in ayurvedic classics, which disrupts the Women hood in various ways. Health care Of woman is very important. Any disorders That hampers the general, mental as well as The reproductive health of woman should Be considered with care and required Medical attention. Female body is highly Complex and delicate. Because of special Reproductive role, women are at risk of Some distinct female disorders. *Kaphaja Yoni vyapad* is one of those diseases. Vaginal discharge means *yonni strava* is Seen as a symptom in case of this disease. As the Stree is mula of reproduction, Stree Is important part of our society and family. Being Daughter, wife, mother, carrier Oriented women, she plays different roles And follows social and family Responsibilities. Nature has given special Role to Stree to become mother.^[1] Along With that as today's women is carrier Oriented she is becoming independent,

Making her own decision and thus making Her own space in the society. Thus in this Fast life she is subjected to all sorts of Physical and mental hardship. Due to Change in lifestyle, modern food habits of Fast food, junk food she is unable to follow The rules of *Dincharya*, *Rutucharya*, *Rajaswala*, *Rutumati* and *Sutikaparicharya* Which are explained by Acharyas for Women's health. Thus she is prone to Various *yonirogas* one of which is *Yonigat Shewtapicchilsrava*, *Yonikandu*, *Yonigata Alpavedana* which are features of *Kaphaj Yoni vyapad*. *Yonivyapadas* are related to *Tryavartayoni*.^[2] *Yonivyapadas* causes *Apatyavighat*, because *vikruti* of *Kshetra*, Of *Tryavartayoni* causes *Garbhpat*, *Garbhastrva*, *Leenagarbh*, *Garbhvikruti*.^[3] *Yonivyapada* has been described in Various Literatures of Ayurveda viz. *Charak Samhita (Chi.30)*, *Sushrut Samhita(U.38)*, *Ashtang Hridaya (U33)*, *Ashtang Sangraha (Uttarshan38)* *Madhav Nidan(63)*, *Sharangdhar Samhita (Purvakhanda7)* *Kashyap Samhita (Su.27)* *Bhavprakash*

& *Yogratnakar (Yoniraogadhi Kara)*. As in our country due to poor nutrition, Multiple childbirth, low socio-economic Status, poverty, population growth, Negligence of proper hygiene, many Women are anemic, malnourished, ill-Health. So they are prone to various *Yonirogas* like *Kaphajayonivyapada*. Among the 20 *Yoni Vyapats*, *Kaphaj Yoni Vyapat* is explained under the Classification of the *Kaphapradhana Yoni Vyapat* characterized by clinical features of *KaphaVridhhi*.

Characteristics of this *Kaphaj Yonivyapad* Are:
Kandu(itching)
PicchilaSrava in Yoni (mucoïd Discharge).

The aggravated *Kapha* along with Abnormal functions of *Vata* reaches the Reproductive organs of women, results in:

Kandu (itching in vulva and Vagina)
Sheeta (discharge without warmth)
Picchila (slimy mucoïd discharge)
 Mild pain Pallor of the Vulva.

The symptoms of *Kaphaj Yoni Vyapat* Mentioned in Ayurveda literature appear Similar to the clinical features of vulvo Vaginal candidiasis. The second most Common infections among reproductive Aged women with a single incidence of 75%, and two or more episodes in 45% of Women. *Candida albicans* is responsible For 85% to 90% of the vaginal yeast Infections. *Vulvovaginitis*, it is a situation In which the vagina gets sore and irritated.

Specific causes of kaphaj yoni vyapat

Charak

- *Mithyachar* (abnormal diet and mode of life)
- *Pradusta -Artava*(abnormalities of artava)
- *Bijadosha* (abnormalities of Bija)
- *Daivakopa* (curses or anger of god)

Sushrut

Mithyachar

- *Pradusta-Artava*
- *Bijadosha*
- *Daivakopa*
- *Prabridhdhalinga-Purushatisevana*

Vagbhat

- *Dustabhojan*
- *Bisamangasayan-*
- *Bhrisamaithunsevan*
- *Dustaartava*
- *Apadravya prayog*
- *Bijadosha*
- *Daivata*

These are the general *Nidan* of *Yoni Vyapat*. If we observe the *Nidan* of *kaphaja yoni vyapat* then it will be Cleared that in classics *Nidan* for *Kaphaja Yoni vyapat* is not mentioned directly. Excessive consumption of foods and Substances which cause oozing and serous Effusion

in the body and also other *kapha* Aggravating foods and activities on regular Basis by woman causes aggravation of *Kapha*.

Kapha Dosha is composed of earth and Water elements. It has coolness and Heaviness as its basic qualities. Any diet or Activity that causes increase of coolness And heaviness naturally increases *Kapha Dosha*.

Qualities of Kapha

Guru
Shita
Mridu
Snigdha
Madhur
Sthira
Picchila

So, the qualities agonist to these can vitiate *Kapha*.

Kapha increasing factors

Factors that cause *Kapha Dosha* increase:

Guru ahara – excessive consumption Of heavy to digest foods

Madhura – excessive consumption of Foods which have sweet taste.

Atisnigdha – excessive consumption of Unctuous or oily foods (fried foods). Oiliness (unctuousness) is a *KaphaDosha* quality. Hence, any thing That is oily and fatty aggravates *KaphaDosha*.

Dugdha – Excessive consumption of Milk. Cow milk, being sweet in taste And heavy to Digest, increases *KaphaDosha*.

Ikshu– Excessive consumption of Sugarcane and its derivatives like Sugar, jaggery (molasses) etc

Bhakshya – High caloric foods

Coconut milk – Being sweet and heavy To digest increases *KaphaDosha*.

Drava – Excessive consumption of Liquid foods. This is due to increase of Water elements.

Dadhi – Excessive consumption of Curds, especially sweet curds.

Atinidra – Excessive sleeping

Apupa – Excessive consumption of Stuffed foods

Sarpi – Excessive consumption of ghee, Ghee foods. Ghee is known to calm Down *Vata* and

PittaDosha. In higher doses, due to its Unctuousness, it increases *KaphaDosha*.

Divaswap - early part of the day. If We divide day time into three parts, the First part of the Day is dominated by *KaphaDosha*.

Bhuktamatre – immediately after the Consumption of the food. If we divide

The digestion Process into three parts, the first Part of the digestion is dominated by

KaphaDosha.

Vasanta – spring season.

Avyayama – lack of exercise, sedentary Lifestyle etc. Anything that causes Increase of Heaviness and stability increases *KaphaDosha*.

1. DISEASE REVIEW

Yonivyapad

Yonivyapad is consists of two words "*Yoni*" and "*Vyapad*"

The word "*Yoni*" refers to *karnam, hetu, utpattistanam*

The word "*Vyapad*" refers to *sankatam, vyadhi, vikruti, vicar* Derivation of *yonivyapad*

The word *Yoni-Vyapad* refers to the diseases of the *Yoni*.

The illness based on the female genital tract is *Yonivyapad*.

The word *Yonivyapad* means "the diseases of complete reproductive system as well as the diseases of the genital organs of woman."

Yoni is very important organ for process like fertilization, implantation and birth process. If *Yoni* gets not proper functioning or there is a defect in anatomical structures, then there is pathological process will be start we called as *Yonivyapada*. Total *Yonivyapada* is 20 in number.

Etiology

"विंशतिव्यापदो योनेनिर्दिष्टा रोगसंग्रहे ॥

मिथ्याचारेणे ताः स्त्रीणां प्रदुष्टेनार्त्वेन च ।

जायन्ते बीजदोषञ्च दैवाञ्च शृणु ताः पृथक् ॥" (च.चि. ३०/७,८)³

" विंशतिव्यापदो योनेजयिन्ते दुष्टभोजनात् ॥" (अ.ह. उ. ३३/२७)⁵

Etiology and Pathophysiology

According to Ayurvedic Literature: Intake of *Kaphakara* (muco-genic) and *AbhishyandiAhara* (obstructive/congestive Foods) causes *Shleshmala Yoni Vyapat*.

AbhishyandiAhara leads to qualitative

Aggravation of *Kaphadosha* and *SrotomalinyakaraAhara* (systemic Pollutants) leads to *Kaphavridhi*.

Mithyachara includes both the *Mithyaahara* (abnormal diet) –intake of Excessive, non-congenial, unwholesome, Unhygienic and incompatible food and *Mithya vihara* (abnormal mode of the life)

Coitus in abnormal body postures, Stressful life which also leads to *VataVridhi*.

Vata is the prime *dosha* for the Manifestations of diseases pertaining to Female reproductive organs. In *Kaphaja Yoni vyapat*, intake *AbhishyandhiAhara* leads to *Agnimandya* leading to *Rasadhatudushti*. Thus *Snigdhatwa, Guru, Picchilaguna* of abnormal *Kapha* along With that the *Chalaguna of Vata*(excessive Secretary activity) results in manifestation Of *Kaphaja Yoni vyapat* charecterised by *Snigdha, Sheeta, Picchilasrava* in *Yoni*.

Yonivyapad samanya samprapti

"न हि वातादृते योनिर्नारीणां संग्रह्यति ॥" (च.चि. ३०/११५)

All acharyas have agreed that there is no *Yonivyapadas* without a vitiated *Vata dosha*. "The genital organs of women do not get afflicted without the aggravated *Vata dosha*." (Ch.Chi 30/115)

Vata prakopaka ahara also plays important role in manifestation of disease

Kaphaj yonivyapad

"कफोऽभिष्यन्दिभिवृद्धो योनिं चदूषयेत् स्त्रियाः।

सु कुर्यात् पिच्छिलां शीतां कण्डुग्रस्ताल्पवेदनाम् ॥

पाण्डुवर्णा तथा पाण्डुपिच्छिलात्वाहिनीम् ॥" (च.चि. ३०/१३, १४)³

"श्लेष्मला पिच्छिला योनिः कण्डुयुक्ताऽतिशीतला ॥ (सु.सं.उ. ३८/१७)³

कफोऽभिष्यन्दिभिः कुद्धः कुर्याद्व्योनिमवेदनाम् ।

शीतलां कण्डुलां पाण्डुपिच्छिलां तद्विधुत्सुतिम् ॥

सा व्यापच्छलैष्मिकी" (अ.ह. उ. ३३/४४)⁶

SampraptiGhatak

Dosha – *Vata + kapha*

Dushya – *Rasa, Rakta&mamsa*

Srotas – *Rasavaha, artavaha, Raktavaha*

Srotodustilakshan – *Atipravriti*

Adhistan – *Yoni*

Rogamarga – *Abhyantara*

Samprapti

Nidan

↓
Vitiation of *Kapha* with *Vata*

↓
Kapha starts to accumulate in its own Space

↓
This accumulation leads to *Prakopaavasthaa*

↓
This provoked and spread *Kapha* there After gets lodgement in the

Artavavahasrota or in the genital system.

↓
Causes symptoms of *Kaphaja Yoni Vyapat*

DRUG REVIEW

"मुद्गपुष्पं सखदिरं पथ्या जातीफलं तथा। वृकीपूगं च संचूर्ण्य
वत्सपूतं क्षिपेद्भद्रे ॥ योनिर्भवति संकीर्णा न स्त्रवेच्च जलं ततः
॥७७॥" (यो. र. उ. ४३/७)⁷

MUDGAPUSHPA

“मुद्गपर्णी हिमा रूक्षा तिक्ता स्वादुश्च शुक्रला ।
चक्षुष्या क्षतशोथघ्नी ग्राहिणी ज्वरदाहनुत् ।
दोषत्रयहरी लघ्वी ग्रहण्यर्थोऽतिसारजित् ॥४६॥” भावप्रकाश

Gundharma

Rasa -Madhura, Tikta

Guna-Laghu, Snigdha

Viry-Sheeta

Vipaka-Madhura

Dosha effect-Pacifies Vata & Pitta

Charaka Samhita

Mudgaparni is mentioned in the *Brimhana* (nourishing) and *Balya* (strength-promoting) group.

Doshas

1. *Vata Dosha* - Pacifies *Vata Mudgaparni* has *snigdha* (unctuous) and *balya* (strengthening) qualities, which help reduce dryness and instability.
2. *Pitta Dosha* - Mildly pacifies *Pitta* Its cooling (*sheeta virya*) nature helps soothe excess heat, inflammation, and irritability associated with *Pitta*.
3. *Kapha Dosha* - Generally neutral / slightly increasing if overused Because of its nourishing and slightly heavy qualities, excessive use may mildly increase *Kapha*, but in balanced doses it usually does not aggravate it significantly

Dhatus

1.*Rasa Dhatu* - Nourishes and replenishes *Rasa* Due to *Madhura rasa & vipaka*, it promotes *dhatu poshana*. Acts in *dhatu kshaya* (depletion) and general debility. *Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana 28/7 – Madhura rasa* nourishes all *dhatu*s

Ashtanga Hridaya Sutrasthana 10 – Brimhana dravyas enhance *Rasa*

2. *Rakta Dhatu* - Supports and cools *Rakta Sheeta virya* helps in pacifying *Pitta in Rakta* Maintains quality of blood without aggravation.

Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana 26/43 – Cooling substances support Rakta & Pitta balance

3. *Mamsa Dhatu* - Promotes muscle growth (*Brimhana* effect) Nourishing and strengthening properties aid tissue bulk.

Charaka Samhita Chikitsasthana 1 – Brimhana herbs improve *Mamsa dhatu*

4. *Meda Dhatu* - Moderate nourishment *Guru & Snigdha guna* increase lubrication and stability Excess use may mildly increase *Meda*

Ashtanga Hridaya Sutrasthana 11 – Snigdha and Guru dravyas nourish *Meda*

5. *Asthi Dhatu* - Indirect strengthening Proper nourishment of earlier *dhatu*s leads to healthy *Asthi* formation.

Charaka Samhita Chikitsasthana 15 – Sequential dhatu nourishment (*Dhatu Parinama Siddhanta*)

6. *Majja Dhatu* - Supports *Majja* via *Vata* pacification *Snigdha* and *Madhura* qualities stabilize nervous tissue. *Sushruta Samhita Sutrasthana 15 – Snigdha dravyas* nourish *Majja*

7. *Shukra Dhatu* - Enhances fertility and vitality *Madhura* rasa and *Brimhana* action improve *Shukra*. *Charaka Samhita Chikitsasthana 2 – Shukra* is nourished by *Madhura dravyas*

Mala

1.*Purisha* - Mildly increases and softens stool *Madhura rasa + Snigdha guna* → promote *mridu mala pravritti*. Helps in *Vata*-related constipation (*ruksha mala*).

Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana 26

2. *Mutra* - Maintains normal urination

Cooling (*Sheeta virya*) helps in soothing urinary tract.

Ashtanga Hridaya Sutrasthana → *Sheeta dravya* → *Pitta* pacification in *Mutravaha srotas*

3. *Sveda* - Mildly reduces excessive sweating *Sheeta* nature → reduces heat → decreases excess sweating.

KHADIR

“खदिरः कषायस्तिक्तो रुक्षो लघुश्च शीतलः।

कुष्ठकण्डूविषघ्नश्च रक्तदोषविनाशनः॥” भाव प्रकाश

Khadira is considered one of the main drugs for treating skin diseases and is used in decoctions and formulations for blood purification. *Khadira* decoction is recommended for *Kushta*, *Kandu* (itching), and *Rakta Dushti*.

Sushruta Samhita, Mentioned in management of *Kushta* and wound care.

Sushruta Samhita Chikitsasthana 9 – Kushta Chikitsa *Khadira* is used in *Kashaya* (decoction), *lepa* (paste), and *snana* (medicated bath)

Ashtanga Hridaya Chikitsasthana 19

Khadira preparations are used to purify blood and treat chronic skin diseases.

Dosha

1. *Kapha Dosha* — *Kapha Shamak*, *Kashaya rasa + Ruksha guna* → reduce *Kapha* (moist, heavy qualities), Useful in: *Kaphaja* skin diseases,
2. *Pitta Dosha* — *Pitta Shamak*, *Tikta/Kashaya rasa* → reduce heat and inflammation, *Raktapitta*, *Daha* (burning sensation), *Pittaja kushtha*.
3. *Vata Dosha* — *Vata Vardhak* (can increase *Vata*), *Ruksha* (dry) and *Laghu* (light) qualities → may aggravate *Vata*

Dhatu

1. *Rasa Dhatu - Shoshana* (absorbing) and mild purification *Kashaya rasa* reduces excess *kleda* (fluidity) in *rasa*
2. *Rakta Dhatu - Rakta shodhaka* (blood purifier), *Rakta stambhaka* (controls bleeding)
Useful in: Skin disorders, *Raktapitta*
3. *Mamsa Dhatu - Kashaya rasa* causes *sankochana* (contraction), Helps in: Healing ulcers, Reducing discharge from wound
4. *Meda Dhatu - Ruksha* (dry) and *Laghu* (light) reduce excess fat (*meda*)
Useful in: Obesity, *Meda dushti*
4. *Asthi Dhatu* -No strong direct nourishing effect
5. *Majja Dhatu* - Excess *ruksha guna* may: Reduce unctuousness of *majja*
6. *Shukra Dhatu - Kashaya and ruksha* may: Decrease *shukra* if taken excessively

Mala

1. *Purisha* (Stool) - *Kashaya rasa* → *Grahi* (absorptive, binding action) *Ruksha guna* → reduces excessive moisture in stool
Helps in: *Atisara* (diarrhea), *Grahani* disorders (malabsorption with loose stools)

2. *Mutra* (Urine) - *Kapha-Pitta shamana*, Reduction of inflammation in urinary system
Helpful in: Mild urinary disorders associated with *Pitta* (burning, infection)

3. *Sweda* (Sweat) - *Kashaya + Ruksha* ग → reduce excessive sweating Absorbs *kleda* (moisture), Useful in: Excess sweating (*Atisweda*), Oozing skin conditions

HARITAKI

“पथ्या मज्जनि स्वादुः स्नायु अम्लो व्यवस्थितः ।

वृत्ते तिक्तः त्वचि कटुः अस्थिस्थ तुवरो रसः ॥” भावप्रकाश

In Ayurveda, *Haritaki* is one of the most important medicinal fruits. Its *Guna-Dharma* (properties) are described in classical texts like *Charaka Samhita* and *Bhavaprakasha*.

Gunadharm

1. *Rasa - Kashaya* (Also has five *rasas* except *Lavana* (*Madhura*, *Amla*, *Katu*, *Tikta*, *Kashaya*).
2. *Guna - Laghu, Ruksha*
3. *Virya - Ushna Virya*
4. *Vipaka - Madhura Vipaka*

From Bhavaprakasha

“*Haritaki kashaya pradhana laghu ruksha ushna virya madhura vipaka tridosahara.*”

Meaning: *Haritaki* is mainly astringent in taste, light and dry in quality, hot in potency, sweet in post-digestive effect, and pacifies all three *doshas*.

In Ayurveda, *Haritaki* is considered a powerful *Rasayana* drug that positively influences the *Sapta Dhatu* (seven body tissues). Because it improves *Agni* (digestion) and clears *Ama* (toxins), it indirectly nourishes all tissues.

Dosha

1. *Vata Dosha - Haritaki* performs *Anulomana* (downward movement of *Vata*).
2. Relieves constipation, abdominal distension, and gas.
3. *Pitta Dosha* - Its *Madhura Vipaka* helps maintain *Pitta* balance and supports digestion.
4. *Kapha Dosha* - Due to *Ruksha* and *Laghu Guna*, it reduces excess *Kapha* and heaviness.

Dhatu

1. *Rasa Dhatu* - Improves digestion and absorption. Helps proper formation of nutrient fluid.
2. *Rakta Dhatu* - Helps detoxification and supports healthy blood circulation.
3. *Mamsa Dhatu* - Improves metabolism and prevents accumulation of toxins in muscles.
4. *Meda Dhatu* - Reduces excess fat and helps regulate lipid metabolism.
5. *Asthi Dhatu* - By improving nutrient assimilation, it indirectly supports bone nourishment.
6. *Majja Dhatu* - Helps detoxification and supports nerve strength.
7. *Shukra Dhatu* - As a *Rasayana*, it promotes reproductive health and vitality.

Mala

1. *Purisha* - Acts as mild laxative (*Anulomana*), Helps proper evacuation and relieves constipation.
2. *Mutra* - Improves metabolism and helps proper urinary elimination.
3. *Sveda* - By improving metabolism and circulation, it supports normal sweat

JATIPHALA

“जातीफलं रसे तिक्तं तीक्ष्णोष्णं रोचनं लघु ।

कटुकं दीपनं ग्राहि स्वर्त्यं श्लेष्मानिलापहम् ॥ ४८ ॥

निहन्ति मुखवैरस्यं मलदौर्गन्ध्यकृष्णताः ।

कृमिकासवमिश्वासशोषपीनसहृद्गुजः ॥ ४९ ॥

“जातीफलस्य त्वक् प्रोक्ता जातीपत्री भिषग्वरैः ।

जातीपत्री लघुः स्वादुः कटूष्णा रुचिवर्णकृत् ।

कफकासवमिश्वासतृष्णाकृमिविषापहा ॥ ५० ॥” (भा. प्र.)

1. *Rasa - Tikta, Katu, Kashaya*

2. *Guna - Laghu, Ruksha*

3. *Virya - Ushna Virya*

4. *Vipaka - Katu Vipaka*

5. *Dosha Karma - Vata Dosha, Kapha Dosha*

May increase *Pitta Dosha* if taken in excess because of its *Ushna* nature.

Dosha

1. *Vata Dosha - Ushna* (hot) potency reduces *Vata*-related symptoms like abdominal pain and gas.
2. *Kapha Dosha - Laghu and Ruksha* qualities help reduce heaviness, mucus, and sluggish digestion.
3. *Pitta Dosha* - Because of its hot nature, excessive intake may increase *Pitta*.

Dhatu

1. *Rasa Dhatu - Deepana and Pachana* improve digestion and nutrient absorption, supporting healthy Rasa formation.
2. *Rakta Dhatu* - By improving metabolism, it helps maintain proper circulation and blood quality.
3. *Mamsa Dhatu* - Proper digestion and nutrient assimilation support muscle nourishment.
4. *Meda Dhatu -Laghu and Ruksha* properties help regulate excess *Meda* and *Kapha* accumulation.
5. *Asthi Dhatu* - By improving *Dhatu* metabolism, it indirectly supports bone nourishment.
6. *Majja Dhatu - Jatiphala* has *Medhya* and *Nidrajanana* effects, supporting nervous system balance.
7. *Shukra Dhatu* -Traditionally considered supportive for reproductive strength and vitality when used in proper dosage.

Mala

1. *Purisha* - Acts as *Grahi* (absorbs excess fluid in intestines).Useful in *Atisara* (diarrhea) and *Grahani* disorders.
2. *Mutra* - Indirectly supports urinary balance through improved digestion and metabolism.
3. *Sveda* - *Ushna* nature promotes mild sweating and improves metabolism.

PATHA

“पाठोष्णा कटुका तीक्ष्णा वातक्षेप्यहरी लघुः ।

हन्ति शूलज्वरच्छर्दिकुशातीसारहृद्भुजः ।

दाहकण्डू विषश्वासकुमिगुल्मगरत्रणान् ॥” भाव प्रकाश

1. *Rasa (Taste) -Tikta* (bitter), *Katu* (pungent)
2. *Guna - Laghu – light, Ruksha*
3. *Virya - Ushna Virya*
4. *Vipaka - Katu Vipaka*

Dosha

1. *Vata Dosha -Patha* has *ruksha* (dry) and *laghu* (light) qualities → may increase *Vata* if used excessively, its *ushna virya* (heating) helps in mild *Vata* disorders when associated with *Ama* (toxins).
2. *Pitta Dosha* -Bitter (*tikta*) and astringent (*kashaya*) tastes help pacify *Pitta*. Though it has heating potency, its *Pitta*-reducing tastes dominate.
3. *Kapha Dosha* -Light (*laghu*), dry (*ruksha*), and hot (*ushna*) qualities strongly reduce *Kapha*.

Dhatu

1. *Rasa Dhatu -Deepana and Pachana* improve digestion and absorption, supporting proper *Rasa* formation.
2. *Rakta Dhatu -Tikta Rasa* helps purify blood and maintain *Rakta* quality.
3. *Mamsa Dhatu* -By improving metabolism and reducing *Ama*, it supports healthy muscle tissue.
4. *Meda Dhatu - Laghu and Ruksha* properties help reduce excess *Meda* and *Kapha* accumulation.
5. *Asthi Dhatu* - Proper *Dhatu* metabolism indirectly supports bone nourishment.

6. *Majja Dhatu* - By improving metabolic balance, it helps maintain healthy *Majja*.
7. *Shukra Dhatu* -Proper digestion and tissue formation indirectly support reproductive health.

Mala

1. *Mala -Patha* has *Deepana and Pachana* properties, which improve digestion. It also has *Grahi* action that helps absorb excess fluid in intestines. Therefore it is useful in *Atisara* (diarrhea) and *Grahani* disorders.
2. *Mutra -Patha* has *Mutrala* (diuretic) property. It helps proper urinary elimination and is useful in urinary disorders and infections.
3. *Sveda* - Due to its *Ushna Virya*, it improves metabolism and indirectly supports normal sweating.

PUGA

“आर्द्रं तद्वर्षभिष्यन्दि वह्निदृष्टिहरं स्मृतम्।

पूगं गुरु हिमं रूक्षं कषायं कफपित्तजित् ।

मोहनं दीपनं रुच्यमास्यवैरस्यनाशनम्॥

स्विन्नं दोषत्रयच्छेदि वृढमध्यं तदुत्तमम्॥” भा.प्र

1. *Rasa - Kashaya*
2. *Guna – Laghu, Ruksha*
3. *Virya - Sheeta Virya*
4. *Vipaka - Katu Vipak*
5. *Dosha Karma -Kapha Dosha, Pitta Dosha*

Dosha

1. *Kapha Doṣa* -Due to *kashaya* rasa and *ruksh guna*, *Puga* reduces: Excess mucus, Heaviness and lethargy. Hence, it is considered *Kapha-hara*. Useful in: *Kaphaja* disorders (e.g., excessive salivation, oral mucus conditions)
2. *Pitta Doṣa* - Its *shita virya* Reducing heat Controlling bleeding tendencies. Beneficial in:*Raktapitta* (bleeding disorders), Burning sensations
3. *Vata Doṣa -Ruska* (dry) and *laghu* (light) qualities. It can: Increase dryness, Promote constipation or gas if overused

Dhatu

4. *Rasa Dhatu* -Its *Grahi* property helps proper absorption of nutrients and prevents excess fluid loss.
5. *Rakta Dhatu* -The *Kashaya Rasa* helps in *Raktastambhana* (stopping bleeding) and maintaining blood stability.
6. *Mamsa Dhatu* -By improving digestion and reducing *Kapha*, it helps maintain proper muscle tissue metabolism.
7. *Meda Dhatu -Laghu and Ruksha* qualities help reduce excess *Meda* and *Kapha* accumulation.
8. *Asthi Dhatu* - By maintaining proper metabolism and tissue stability, it indirectly supports *Asthi Dhatu*.
9. *Majja Dhatu* - Balanced metabolism helps maintain healthy *Majja Dhatu*.

10. *Shukra Dhatu* -By maintaining tissue stability and metabolism, it indirectly supports reproductive tissue.

Mala

1. *Purisha -Puga has Grahi* action, which absorbs excess intestinal fluid. Helps control *Atisara* (diarrhea) and improves stool consistency. Supports proper bowel function.
2. *Mutra* - By balancing *Kapha* and *Pitta* and improving metabolism, it helps maintain proper urinary elimination.
3. *Sveda* -Through improved metabolic activity, it indirectly supports normal sweating.

Probable Mode of Action

Probable mode of action of mudgapushpadi kwath yonidhawan on the bases of dravya Guna panchaka.

Tikta rasa: It acts as *krimighna, kandughna, lekhana, kleda puya pitta shleshma upashoshana, sthirikarana of mamsa and twak, sukshma guna pradhana*; So it removes the damaged epithelial cells, pus, inflammatory secretion like exudates, bacteria etc.

Kashaya rasa: *Kashaya rasa* dominating the *vayu* and *prithvi mahabhoota*, it does have *samshamana, sangrahi, sandhanakara, ropana, soshana, sthambana, shleshmapittaprashamana, kleda upashoshana* properties.

Katu rasa: It acts as *kledashoshaka, kandu nashaka, krimi nashaka*, scraping of *dushita mamsa*, dilatation of *srotas*.

Laghu: *Laghu guna* is predominant of *agni* and *akasha mahabhoota*. It acts as *kapha shamana, mala kshaya*.

Ruksha: *Ruksha guna* is predominant of *vayu mahabhoota*, it does the **shoshana** of increased *jala mahabhoota and kapha shamana*.

Ushna: It does *pachana, vilayana, vatakapha shaman*, it pacifies *vata* dominance.

Teekshna: *Tikshna guna* is *agni* and *vayu mahabhoota pradhana*.

Dosha: *Kapha* being *pradhana dosha in shleshmala yonivyapat*, it gets mitigated by *katu, tikta kashaya rasa and laghu, ruksa, ushna and teekshna gunas*; *Ushna veerya of yoga* helps in mitigating *vata dosha*.

Dushya: *Laghu & ruksha guna* helps in *srotoshodhana* and helps for fresh blood circulation to the affected area.

Agni: *deepana (katu, kashaya rasa, ushna and teekshna guna)* and *pachana (tiktarasa and ushna guna)*. This process increases the *jataragni* and *dhatvagni* and helps in bringing the *vitiated doshas* to normal form. Because of *grahi, stambhana (kashaya rasa)* action does act as

drava shoshana, decreasing the *sraava*, thus helping in *samprapti vighatana of kaphaj yonivyapat*

DISCUSSION

The term *Kaphaj Yonivyapat* is related to *Ayurvedic* medicine, specifically concerning health Issues that arise due to the imbalance of the *Kapha Dosha* in women's reproductive health. *Kapha* is Primarily associated with the earth and water Elements. It governs structure, stability, lubrication, And the body's immune system. When *Kapha* is in Balance, it promotes strength, vitality, and endurance. However, when it becomes imbalanced, it can lead to Various health conditions, including issues related the reproductive system. *Yonivyapat* refers to Disorders or ailments related to the female Reproductive system. These conditions can range From menstrual disorders, infertility, vaginal Infections, and other gynecological issues. *Kaphaj Yonivyapat* occurs when there is an imbalance or Excess of the *Kapha dosha* in the reproductive organs Which affects the normal functioning of the female Reproductive system. Heavy, excessive vaginal Discharge (possibly thick and white), Irregular Menstrual cycles or delayed periods, Weight gain and Sluggish metabolism, excessive fatigue or lethargy. One of the core strengths of *Ayurveda* is its Holistic approach. Unlike conventional medicine, Which may focus solely on treating symptoms, *Ayurveda* aims to restore balance at the root cause. In The case of *Kaphaj Yonivyapat*, treatment involves Addressing the individual's unique constitution, Lifestyle, and environment. This approach ensures Long-term healing and prevention. *Kaphaj Yonivyapat* is a disorder resulting from an excess of *Kapha* in the female reproductive system. By Understanding the causes, recognizing the symptoms, And implementing *Ayurvedic* treatments that focus On diet, herbal remedies, and lifestyle changes, this Condition can be effectively managed. The *Ayurvedic* Approach not only addresses the physical symptoms But also ensures the emotional and spiritual well-Being of the individual, making it a truly holistic System of healing.

CONCLUSION

Maintaining reproductive health is essential For overall well-being and fertility. *Kaphaja yoni Vyapat* is the one of the commonest problem among Women of reproductive age as well as menopausal Age . As per *ayurveda kaphaj yonivyapat* caused by Excessive *khaf dosha*. The better management of *Sleshmiki yoni Vyapat* is *Sleshmahara chikista* which Has proven results in *Ayurveda* by maintaining of Proper hygiene and taking appropriate food in time Taking proper sleep and doing regular exercise can Help in maintaining the reproductive health. As per *Ayurveda* treatment should contains the *nidana Parivarjana, Agni deepana, ama pachana, Vatanulomana, sthanika dosha nirharana Chikitsa*. The Holistic framework provided by *Ayurveda* offers avaluable perspective on maintaining reproductive health in women.

REFERENCE

1. Premvati Tiwari, Ayurvediya Prasiti Tantra Avum Strirog, Part-II, chaukhamba orientalia Publication, Varanasi 2nd Edition 2000, Reprint 2022; 1: 10-13.
2. Premvati Tiwari, Ayurvediya Prasiti Tantra Avum Strirog, Part-II, chaukhamba orientalia Publication, Varanasi 2nd Edition 2000, Reprint, 2022; 1: 18-19.
3. Acharya vidyadhar Shukla, Charak samhita, part-2, Vaidyamanorama Hindi commentary By Acharya priyvat Sharma, marathi translation by Acharya Shankar kale, chaukhambha prakashan, Delhi. Reprint, 2016; 739,740,754.
4. Acharya priyavat sharma, Dravyaguna vigyan, chaukhamba prakashan reprint year, 2001; 745,626,156,674,485.
5. Nirmala commentary by Acharya Bramhannda Tripathi, Vagbhata Ashtanga Hridaya, chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, Reprint, 2019; 1128, 1132.
6. Kaviraj Ambikadutta Shastri, Sushruta Samhita, part 2, Chaukhambha Publication, reprint-2013, Uttara tantra 38/9, 228,231.
7. Bhisgranth Bramhashankar Shastri, Yogratnakar, Vidyotini Hindi Commetry by Vaidya Lakshmipati Shastri, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Reprint 1999 Yonivyapad Chikitsa, 411.
8. Bramhanand tripathi, Ashtang sangraha uttartantra, Chaukhambha surbharati prakashan Varanasi 2015 chapter 38, shlok no.34.
9. Brahmanand Tripathi, Shargdhar smhita, Madhyama khanda, Adhyaya 2nd shlok no. 1-3, choukhamba surbharti prakashan, Varanasi reprint, 2017; 90.
10. Acharya Vagbhaṭa, Ashtanga Hridaya, commentaries of Sarvangasundara of Arunadatta and Ayurveda Rasayana of Hemadri, Chaukamba Subharati Prakashan, Varanasi, Uttarasthana, 34/61: 901.
11. Ashok Lamani & Ramadevi G, comprehensive Review of Kaphaj Yonivyapad, Etiology, Diagnosis & management Strategies, International Journal Of Ayurveda & Pharma Research (IJAPR), ISSN-2322-0902, March 2024; 2(3): 97-99.
12. Dr. Rekha Rani & Dr. Rashmi Sharma, A conceptual Review of kaphaj yonivyapad (Non Specific vulvo vaginitis), World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (WJPR), ISSN 2277-7105, Nou-2019; 8(13): 348-352.
13. K.C.Mule & Vishakha Pawar, Kaphaj Yonivyapad A Critical Review, World Of Pharmaceutical Research (WJPR), ISSN 2277-7105, Jan. 2022; 11(1): 1636-1639.
14. Joshi YG, Charak Samhita Uttarardha, Chikitsasthan Adhyay no. 30, Yonivyapad Adhyay, Reprint, 2014; Vaidyamitra Prakashan, Shiok no.13, 82, 83, no.674,681,682.